

Importance of English language on the role of foreign household attendants in attaining an electronically safe environment

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ABSTRACT

This research directed to examine the worth of English language on the role of foreign household attendants in attaining an electronically safe environment. Therefore, the household attendants' skillfulness in English language played a vital part in this research. Survey inquiry form was utilized in conducting this descriptive research design. The number of respondents was one hundred forty-five workers from eight (8) purposely selected countries, namely Philippines, India, Nepal, Indonesia, Korea, Pakistan, Thailand, and Malaysia. Illustrative data applying rate dispersal, proportionality, average, normal variation, mean and informative evaluations centered on 5-point range were employed, while T-test and Pearson Correlation were used for inferential statistics. Based on the findings, everyone's achievement is reflected on individual practices and personal related factors which reveal patterns of actions and attributes that establish the connection on its role in attaining an electronically safe environment. Therefore, profiling is very important in the hiring process because household owners can expect that their workers aim at attaining an electronically safe environment while engaging with their tasks. Moreover, the overall results signified that the correlation is significant (2-tailed) at 0.01 level; stating that there is significant relationship involving the personal related factors of the foreign household attendants on the extent of the experienced safety in an electronic environment due to proficiency in English language. The findings further reveal that all items that are positively correlated; meaning its level of influence (increase/decrease) on the extent of experienced of safety is in the same direction. Thus, these variables are congruent in estimating the value of influence on the attainment of electronically safe environment by the foreign household attendants.

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INTRODUCTION

Foreign household attendants play a vital role in performing the household tasks like taking care of the toddlers, tidying the house, and preparing food together with other household works. The hard works that the overseas household attendants' offers have been determined to be essential for keeping the family healthy and productive. The role being performed by foreign household attendants for the success of any employers cannot be questioned (HelperPlace, 2016).

Sometimes, foreign household attendants may not be able to perform some tasks due to language barrier, so addressing the differences is important as well. Also, foreign household attendants are usually from a less developed area, and they may not be familiar working with advanced electronic appliances. Electric shocks can happen; therefore, while hiring them, make sure that understanding to instructions is guaranteed to deal easily with some hazardous situations and be able to avoid such incident (SafeWork SA, 2014).

In this scenario, English language is utilized for added functions better than before. Universally, it is at the primary threshold of technical and methodical advancement. These create elevation to new terms, structural forms and modes of spoken language and text (Based from the Study of Graddol as cited by Crystal, 2012).

One of the key points that has grasped the interest in the current years is the position of English language in directing the person's daily and professional lives. English language has turned into a central figure in this extremely advanced realm; it is a main frame of technical and practical intelligence of people. Recent daily routines of people have also transformed, thus; interaction using English heightens its importance (Madhavi Latha, 2018).

English is also globally renowned as the lingo of all disciplines. For the most part of the acquaintance connected to the safety use of electronic devices, examples shown are in English. It allows everyone to experience the way of life of the world like no other language can do (Casey & Co., 2018). Therefore, educating oneself with English isn't merely for interaction or concentrated reasons; it will also serve as guide for foreign household attendants to acquire understanding of household rules and instructions. That is why this research work desires to know the significance of English to household workers regarding the attainment of an electronically safe environment to show the connection of English language proficiency to the workers' household experiences in different situations especially if they are alone.

Specifically, this study also sought responses to the given queries relating to common personal related factors of the respondents, extent of experienced connection involving the household attendants' personal related factors in attaining an electronically safe environment, significant effects encountered associated with the use of English language in household undertakings, significant difference on the effects encountered and the considerable connection involving the workers' personal related factors as well as the extent of the experienced safety in an electronic environment due to proficiency in English language.

The null hypotheses derived from the specific problems were statistically tested for significance to clarify if there is no significant difference on the effects encountered associated with the use of English language in household undertakings and no significant relationship involving the personal related factors of the accepted household attendants on the extent of the experienced safety in an electronic environment due to proficiency in English language.

Addressing these problems highlights the significant role of education in making English be acquired not only in a customary classroom discussion but also through online and community immersion so that people in all walks of life can benefit from it. It would impart awareness on how to employ one's ingenuity to remain closely informed with basic knowledge applicable to everyday endeavors, and to discover how English works even to the electronic and ordinary tools available in the households. It could give employers hints on their hiring process to determine what procedure should be applied in accepting applicants.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Determining the importance of English language on the role of foreign household attendants in attaining an electronically safe environment is the wide-ranging problem of this research. Specifically, this study also sought responses to the given queries: the common personal related factors of the accepted foreign household attendants such as age, gender, nationality, marital status, edifying qualification, length experience, and proficiency in English language; the extent of experienced connection involving the household attendants' personal related factors in attaining an electronically safe environment and the extent of experienced safety in an electronic environment due to the household attendants' proficiency in English language in view of the following situations especially if they are alone, namely: checking the correct wattage in all fixtures and appliances, detecting if the outlets are overloaded, replacing or repairing damaged electrical cords, keeping used and unused cords tidy and secure to prevent damage, recognizing the importance of unplugging all unused appliances to reduce potential risks, preventing shock by keeping electrical devices and outlets away from water, giving appliances proper space for air circulation to avoid overheating, ensuring that all electrical equipment are properly clean to prevent fire hazards, following appliance instructions for improved electrical safety, and keeping away combustible items from portable heaters and built-in furnaces to prevent potential accidents. Furthermore, the significant effects encountered associated with the use of English language in household undertakings, a significant difference in the effects encountered and a considerable connection involving the personal related factors of the accepted household attendants as well as the extent of the experienced safety in an electronic environment due to proficiency in English language are foremostly considered.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

Household attendants. They are foreign household workers who significantly broadened their involvement to some families in affluent countries. They follow guidelines involving their job, subsistence, and actual circumstances of their lives. If the household workers are alone, the families expect them to perform safely in all domestic undertakings. Workers employed in private homes that are electronically equipped are required to understand the instructions thoroughly (Mansfield, Homolova and Bentwich, 2013). Thus, this study wanted to find out if the instructions are being communicated in English for better understanding.

Skillfulness in English language. Because of stiff competition, many recruiting agencies are aiming to be always ahead in selecting the best recruits; that's why the accepted workers are always striving hard to meet the employers' expectations. Since employees want to stay longer in their respective work, they exhibit expertise otherwise they should expect termination if they don't care to improve their work habits. It means they are hired due to the capabilities required by their employers. Also, to remain secure in their work, the skills of comprehending instructions and interacting appropriately with their employers through the English language should be attained by the foreign household workers particularly if they don't know their employers' native tongue. Their ability to communicate is very important to their employment. Thus, the capacity to convey messages in English is a sign of preparedness in their endeavors especially if they are working abroad (Danao, 2006). Since English is the most frequently utilized means of communication in the world, it is much sought after. Proper English deals with interrelated abilities for meaningful exchange of ideas like motivating, persuading, instructing, expressing, compromising, and interacting with different people using that language.

Electronically safe environment due to English language. In today's modern world, English has become the most common and dominant language used in an electronic environment. It has also become a means of giving instructions, indicating labels, and providing precautionary measures, warnings, and the like in machines, appliances, and other electronic devices. Since it is a universal language, even those countries that consider English as their foreign or second language need to learn it if they want to get access to modern knowledge, scientific research, global communication, and earn a living. Hence, serious steps have been taken to improve the quality of instruction in English to prove its international power (Abdulhafidh, 2015). However, this paper signifies the importance of English to foreign household attendants in performing their role for the attainment of an electronically safe environment.

Importance of English language. Currently, many people devote their time to learning English. Several countries incorporate English in their curriculum, and kids are being taught to speak English even if they are still young. However, what is really the essence of studying English? Even in searching for new work, preparing for a trip, working abroad, increasing career opportunities, or meeting people around the world, studying English can help in dealing with these situations.

These are the reasons why studying English is very significant: (a) English is a means of communication in a global computer network. (b) A person equipped with the skill in English can easily be hired. (c) A medium of communication when coming across new people. (d) Going around the world with a good command of English is a worry-free experience. (e) English serves as a channel for learning people's values, habits, and way of life which are totally different from each other (BCTE, 2020).

The above-cited importance of English only reveals that even foreign household attendants are expected to equip themselves with the skill of the English language which serves as a vehicle for communicating with their employers and in understanding the nature of their work of keeping the household electronically safe.

Household undertakings. People desire to live in a warm, comfortable, and secure home, so they make sure that it is potentially safe and free from hazards. Fortunately, these household undertakings will study and examine the unrecognized harm that may exist in the dwelling place; therefore, all can apply remediation and reside with full contentment. (1) Avoid disregarding protection in managing household dealings. (a) Make sure that all cords are not cluttered in front of doors, stairways or to avoid trips. (b) Hide important equipment/tools in a place where they can simply get. (c) Don't leave lockers and storerooms open when they contain harmful substances. (d) Keep perilous supplies properly. (e) Disconnect electrical devices when not in use.

(2) Keep proper home protection. (a) Make sure to put a safety device and automatic padlock. (b) Attach a gadget that will help to determine the existence of fire. (c) Manage risk by having a plan for urgent situations and make certain that the family members including the household workers are aware of it. (d) Don't post publicly the exact time of leaving and returning home. (e) Affix cameras in the important places of the house.

(3) Get rid of electrical hazards. (a) Change all dented and worn wires and junk defective appliances. (b) Apply proper ways of changing light bulbs. (c) Beware octopus' outlets. (d) Fix electrical connection by an authorized electrician (Safety Team, 2020). Therefore, a household worker should have an understanding of all the typical emergency responses to get rid of potential risks and to maintain safety at home.

Relationship between the employees' profile and the attainment of an electronically safe environment. Employees, even those who are working at home, are the main possessions of every employer. The committed task they portray cannot be undervalued. Thus, bestowing these exceptional qualities via helpful induction and guidance turns into an essential undertaking to boost the workers' approach to carrying out their work (Nassazi, 2013).

Since electrical and technological changes affect the nature of work itself, they have altered the way work is being performed. As the disposition of the job setting persists to shift, recent things have occurred to the person. The labor force is instantly more distinct in all aspects continuously. If employees are sympathetic to these transformations and skilled enough to fit immediately with recent machinery, it can be favorable equally to the workers and managers (Aneesh, 2006). In this case, employees' profiles have a significant connection to how they work in an electronic environment and in attaining safety as well.

Mobile interaction educational applications throughout COVID-19 epidemic: A collected work evaluation-based research. Even though the entire world has come under the influence of a novel pandemic crisis, COVID-19, educational setup, and the whole realm of learning, although suffered, was able to make a major change in the mode of learning. Virtual learning has come into power, which takes into account the crucial role of language-learning mobile applications including their benefits. Many language learning aspirants can download the apps daily.

These apps have a remarkably positive influence on foreign language learners regarding the ease of providing a self-paced learning opportunity along with uplifting the motivational level of language learners. Virtual or distant language learning via mobile apps brings remarkable progress among foreign language learners (Haidov and Soykan, (2022).

This study is relevant in the conducted research since foreign household attendants are being confided to stay at home most of the time. These mobile applications can serve as guides to their endeavors and can provide a self-paced learning opportunity to them. If the role of mobile language learning apps and their potential advantageous impact have been proven significant during the COVID-19 crisis where life is going through various restrictive measures, then it is possible that it could be a very important tool during the household attendants' attainment of an electronically safe environment.

Bilingualism: Its influence on the reading comprehension of college students. Reading performs an immense function in the lives of people. It offers them entry to the world of thought and a mechanism for gaining expertise in various subject areas. Nevertheless, various aspects hinder one from obtaining reading competencies. One of the most controversial issues is the language problem resulting in a subject matter for a national debate. This analysis was performed retaining the application of English and Filipino languages to reveal their substantial impact on the reading comprehension of college students. A true-experimental method of research was used, and it revealed: a) language of instruction does not affect significantly the achievement in reading comprehension of the subjects, b) outcomes of the exams given before and after both investigational and restraint groups steadily displayed that the English and Filipino instructed-experimental and control group performed well in their reading achievement (Lobaton, 2022).

Since the language barrier hinders the use of English in the performance of household duties, bilingualism can lessen the encountered difficulty. Highly technical terms in a modernized environment should be translated into a language convenient to the workers. Disseminated information whether in manuals, brochures, and other sources, subtitles of predominant languages should be applied. This type of approach is substantially important in attaining an electronically safe environment.

Overseas household aides' ability to speak English and learners' English studying achievement in Hongkong. The understanding ability in studying English by 4,352 Grade 4 Hong Kong pupils was verified (Tse et al 2009). The pupils' mothers and fathers accomplished the surveys related to home-based aspects, comprising regular salary, the dialect customarily articulated in the family, parents' work-related standing, and the English-speaking ability of their household aides. Results of assessments showed statistically meaningful influences relating to the comprehension ability of the youngster and the English-speaking skill of the household aide. On the other hand, the correlation was greater between the comprehension ability of the daughter/son and the parents' competence in English language. A statistically substantial variation between the comprehension ability of learners who had English-speaking household aides and those who didn't was demonstrated in the Analysis of variance (ANOVA). It likewise showed statistically substantial variations among the learners' comprehension ability records, the parents' socioeconomic standing (SES), and the mother's occupational reputation.

The second language spoken by the father and mother, immigrant household aides, and kids: Data from Hong Kong. Another research studies the impacts of several linguistic household settings presented by English-speaking and non-English-speaking immigrant household workforce on Hong Kong offspring's capacity to express in English. Findings reveal that English-speaking immigrant domestic aides in employed-mother families intensify youngsters' probability of talking in English by 12% especially if the mother can't speak English but by 25% if the mother can speak English. Non-English-speaking immigrant household aides, nonetheless, are observed to have minor impacts as such. Maturity and educational background are two potentials of English-speaking immigrant household aides that are considerably linked with developments in youngsters' English-speaking capability and their English school training (Tang, 2018).

The reviewed studies provided more insights to the researcher regarding the importance of the English language to foreign workers including its working environment. Relatedness in the present study is in the condition of determining the distinctive features of the English language and of securing a safe environment. Furthermore, the current study is initiated and directed by individual interest and responsive in providing immediate feedback.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In conducting this study, the deployment of a descriptive approach was decided. It is applied to gain data involving the recent states of the events to explain “what occurs” about variable quantity or set in a condition. Further proven by Van Dalen (2019), who cited in his study that description, investigation, recording, analysis, and interpretation of data are important factors in conducting descriptive research, especially in finding responses to the queries regarding the current position of the issue of the research. The researchers’ modified inquiry form was employed and was further confirmed or clarified by consultation.

The respondents of the research were confined to foreign household attendants from purposely selected countries in Asia in the range of the researchers’ knowledge and were identified by several of the researchers’ relatives, social groups, and networks, thus; collecting and repossession of information were completed simply. Likewise, the subjects of this study are overseas workers; it is projected that the English language is being tapped in communicating with them especially if they are not proficient in speaking the native tongue of their employers. In what way the respondents perceive the significant effect associated with the use of the English language in attaining an electronically safe environment was one of the concerns of this study.

The inquiry form was the researchers’ amended method to be applied for the intention of this research. It was based on the statement of the problems and was patterned from the questionnaire used by Asenas (2018) in her study about “Interaction Hindrances: Influences on Environmental Calamity Readiness” and from Slobodzian-Taylor (2015) in her study about “Why Language is Important for Business Growth?” with some changes. A set of questionnaires were sent through a link to the respondents to gather data concerning the problems being studied.

The researchers solicited questions/suggestions from the respondents done through online to get hold of more data and to have greater clarity from them that served as follow-up/lead of the research. Most of the items included in the questionnaire were culled from related literature/studies, instruments, and analysis, particularly the one that was taken from Asenas and Slobodzian-Taylor. The first draft of the questionnaire was shown to three (3) English teachers and researchers at the same time whose skills cannot be doubted due to their competencies as veterans in their field of specialization. Their corrections, suggestions, and comments were used as bases for improving its content, vocabulary, and style. Having been assured of its content, the researchers arranged the questionnaire in its final form. To obtain high reliability, five (5) foreign household attendants who were not the target respondents in the study were asked to answer the questionnaire; and after three (3) days, the same persons underwent the same procedure with the same instrument expected to obtain the result of .75 correlations or pilot test showing $\text{Alpha} = .8380$.

The recent research relied greatly on suitable informers, in this case; the researchers entered the explorative perspective in notified agreement, individual subjects’ endorsement, and interview. This was secured via virtual interaction. Accepted operational processes were pursued before carrying out the research. The researchers, to prevent risks to the authenticity and consistency of the findings, directly checked/tracked these actions. This was done during the Second Trimester of the Academic Year 2021-2022.

The facts collected were categorized and reported in grids. Informative values such as rate of recurrence and proportional allocation were utilized for question number one (S.P.1) which concerned the accepted foreign household attendants’ personal related factors. Mean and Standard Deviation were appropriate for questions two to four (S.P.2-4) which focused on the extent of experienced connection of their profile in attaining an electronically safe environment, the extent of experienced safety due to their proficiency in English language, and the effects encountered associated with the use of English language in household undertakings, respectively. Mean and Rank

were utilized for question number three (S.P.3), and informative rankings of statistics were centered on calculated 5-point Likert range entry which was used for questions two to four (S.P.2-4). On the other hand, T-test was utilized for question number five (S.P.5) to determine the significant difference in the effects encountered associated with the use of English language in household undertakings, and Pearson correlation for question number 6 (S.P.6) concerning the considerable connection of workers' profile as well as the extent of experienced safety in an electronic environment due to proficiency in English language.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A significant difference in the effects encountered associated with the use of English language in household undertakings. Table 1 emphasizes the significant difference in the effects encountered associated with the use of the English language in household undertakings as recognized by the intended population of the study. The gathered typical nonconformity of the household attendants' profile was registered in the same order as shown in the table, namely: age .76489, sex .82710, nationality .81972, civil status .84831, educational qualification .83488, years of service/experience .69701 and skillfulness in English language .74362 paired to the effects encountered with a usual nonconformity of .42614.

The exhibited values established an eminent distribution of a group of marks from its norm in marital rank whilst the years of service/experience group of statistical ratings was attached to its standard. Additional scrutiny of the records exposed that; the effects encountered gained a group of marks integral to its mean while the personal profile's acquired results differed from its mean. Therefore, the lesser the calculated normal nonconformity, the smaller the calculated extent of difference of a group of statistical data; whereas the greater the calculated normal nonconformity, the larger the determined dispersal of a group of statistical data.

Moreover, the effects encountered acquired mean of 4.3917 was observed higher than the mean of age (4.2966), sex (4.2690), nationality (4.3448), civil status (4.3655), and educational qualification (4.3862) while lower than the mean of years of service/experience (4.5448) and skillfulness in the English language (4.5655). Regarding the perceived significant difference in the effects encountered associated with the use of the English language in household undertakings, the 2-tailed t-test at 0.05 level was employed. The one hundred forty-five (145) population exposed a statistically substantial explanation on the sig. (2-tailed) rate of the subsequent points: skillfulness in the English language .002* and years of service/experience .008* indicating the rejection of Ho. While age (.145), sex (.071), nationality (.484), civil status (.699), and educational qualification (.931) accepted a statistically not important analysis on its sig. (2-tailed) rate, denoting Ho is recognized.

The entire thing everyone wants to achieve is reflecting on individual practices and personal related factors to discover patterns of actions and attributes that establish the connection on its role in attaining an electronically safe environment. If these manifestations exist, how will the household owners expect their workers to aim at attaining an electronically safe environment while engaging in their tasks (LeBow, 2018)? Therefore, profiling is very important in the hiring process.

Because of stiff competition, many of the recruiting agencies are aiming to be always ahead in selecting the best recruits; that is why the accepted workers are always striving hard to meet the employers' expectations. Also, to remain secure in their work, the skills of comprehending instructions and interacting appropriately with their employers through the English language should be attained by foreign household workers particularly if they do not know their employers' native tongue. Their ability to communicate is very important to their employment. Thus, the capacity to convey messages in English is a sign of preparedness in their endeavors especially if they are working abroad (Danao, 2006).

Moreover, people desire to live in a warm, comfortable, and secure home, so they make sure that it is potentially safe and free from hazards. The household undertakings that should be understood clearly are the following: avoid disregarding protection in managing household dealings; keep proper home protection and get rid

of electrical hazards (Safety Team, 2020). Since all instructions are translated into English, a household worker who can understand all the typical emergency responses can get rid of potential risks but can maintain safety at home.

Education is projected to be more considerable in recognizing the communication capability of the employees as it provides feedback on their academic strengths and weaknesses. (McNamara, 2006). It is a word usually used by numerical analysts to imply the topmost level of instruction a person has earned and the extent to which an individual has achieved his/her short or long-term educational goals. With the aforementioned information, this study relies on the assumption that the respondent’s ability to speak and understand a certain language is due to his/her educational qualification.

Table 1. Significant Difference on the Effects Encountered

Paired Samples Statistics						
	Items	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Sig. (2-tailed)	Description
Pair 1	age	4.2966	145	.76489	.145	Not statistically significant
	effects	4.3917	145	.42614		
Pair 2	sex	4.2690	145	.82710	.071	Not statistically significant
	effects	4.3917	145	.42614		
Pair 3	nationality	4.3448	145	.81972	.484	Not statistically significant
	effects	4.3917	145	.42614		
Pair 4	Civil status	4.3655	145	.84831	.699	Not statistically significant
	effects	4.3917	145	.42614		
Pair 5	Educ qualification	4.3862	145	.83488	.931	Not statistically significant
	effects	4.3917	145	.42614		
Pair 6	Years of service	4.5448	145	.69701	.008*	Statistically Significant
	effects	4.3917	145	.42614		
Pair 7	Skilfulness	4.5655	145	.74362	.002*	Statistically Significant
	effects	4.3917	145	.42614		

*. Difference is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Considerable connection involving personal related factors of household attendants as well as the extent of the experienced safety in an electronic environment due to proficiency in the English language. Table 2 exemplifies the Pearson correlation results (2-tailed) at 0.01 level obtained between personal related factors and the extent of the experienced safety in an electronic environment due to proficiency in the English language as perceived by the one hundred forty-five (145) respondents.

A quick glimpse at the table reveals significant relationships among the variables, such as: (1) age is statistically correlated to the extent of experienced safety with Pearson correlation .351** and sig. (2-tailed) .000 at 0.01 level; (2) sex is statistically correlated to the extent of experienced safety with Pearson correlation .458** and sig. (2-tailed) .000 at 0.01 level; (3) nationality is statistically correlated to the extent of experienced safety with Pearson correlation .491** and sig. (2-tailed) .000 at 0.01 level; (4) civil status is statistically correlated to the extent of experienced safety with Pearson correlation .507** and sig. (2-tailed) .000 at 0.01 level; (5) educational qualification is statistically correlated to the extent of experienced safety with Pearson correlation .466** and sig. (2-tailed) .000 at 0.01 level; (6) years of service/experience is statistically correlated to the extent of experienced safety with Pearson correlation .469** and sig. (2-tailed) .000 at 0.01 level; and (7) skilfulness in the English language is statistically correlated to the extent of experienced safety with Pearson correlation .533** and sig. (2-tailed) .000 at 0.01 level.

As established from the inclusive outcomes, the relationship is significant (2-tailed) at 0.01 level; therefore, the void supposition asserting that there is no substantial connection involving the personal related factors of the

foreign household attendants on the extent of the experienced safety in an electronic environment as a result of their proficiency in English language is rejected. The findings further disclose that all items that are positively correlated; meaning their level of influence (increase/decrease) on the extent of experienced safety is in the same direction.

Since electrical and technological changes affect the nature of work itself, they have altered the way work is being performed. As the inclination of the job setting persists to shift, the latest things have occurred to the person's mind. The labour force is now more demographically and constantly distinct. If employees are sympathetic to these transformations and skilled to fit instantly with modern machinery, it can be favorable for both the workers and managers (Aneesh, 2006). In this case, employees' profile has a significant connection to how they work in an electronic environment and in attaining safety as well.

In today's modern world, English has become the most common and dominant language used in an electronic environment. It has also become a means of giving instructions, indicating labels, providing precautionary measures, warnings, and the like in machines, appliances, and other electronic devices (Abdulhafidh, 2015). However, this paper signifies the importance of English to foreign household attendants in performing their role for the attainment of an electronically safe environment.

These are the reasons why studying English is very significant: Going around the world with a good command of English is a worry-free experience, and English serves as a channel for learning people's values, habits, and way of life which are totally different from each other (BCTE, 2020). The importance of English only reveals that even foreign household attendants are expected to equip themselves with the skill of English language which serves as a vehicle for communicating with their employers and understanding the nature of their work which is keeping the household electronically safe.

The result further pointed out that one of the goals of selection systems is to make sure that the candidate has a positive experience. Why is an employee's experience valuable? Each stage in the worker's development can be a vital force affecting both custom and feat. Requesting for response at every basic feature supports managers to know how they can help their workers to be productive, and where they can create an opportunity for the workers' success. When performed effectively, it aids employees in attaining their highest ability quickly, holds them to persist with their employers, and makes a real contribution to the employers' lives (Jyothi, 2012).

Table 2. Considerable Connection Involving Various Factors

Items	Extent of experience	Description
Pearson Correlation	.351**	Statistically
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	Correlated
N	145	
Pearson Correlation	.458**	Statistically
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	Correlated
N	145	
Pearson Correlation	.491**	Statistically
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	Correlated
N	145	
Pearson Correlation	.507**	Statistically
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	Correlated
N	145	
Pearson Correlation	.466**	Statistically
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	Correlated
N	145	

Pearson Correlation	.469**	Statistically
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	Correlated
N	145	
Pearson Correlation	.533**	Statistically
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	Correlated
N	145	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In observation of the results displayed, the subsequent inferences are taken:

Significant differences in the effects encountered connected with the utilization of English language in domestic endeavours. Hence, the domestic undertakings that should be understood clearly are the following: avoid disregarding protection in managing household dealings; keep proper home protection and get rid of electrical hazards because people desire to live in a warm, comfortable, and secure home. Since all instructions are translated into English, a household worker who can understand all the typical emergency responses can get rid of potential risks but can maintain safety at home.

Considerable connection involving the personal related factors of the household attendants as well as the extent of the experienced safety in an electronic environment due to proficiency in the English language. Based on the overall results, the relationship is noteworthy (2-tailed) at 0.01 degree; therefore, the void supposition asserting that there is no important connection involving the personal related factors of the foreign household attendants on the extent of the experienced safety in an electronic environment as a result of their proficiency in the English language is rejected. The findings further disclose that all items that are positively correlated; meaning their level of influence (increase/decrease) on the extent of experienced safety is in the same direction. Thus, there are circumstances where these variables are congruent in estimating the value of influence on attaining an electronically safe environment.

Based on the results and inferences, the subsequent suggestions are presented for deliberation:

The institutions must conduct the following activities regularly such as formal and informal meetings/focus group discussions with the Programme Industry Advisory Panel (PIAP), benchmarking, market scoping, and different forms of surveys to determine the recent needs of the labour market. These inputs along with the HEC thrusts will serve as bases for the institutions' program review and enhancement to ensure that the courses offered are in demand and aligned to the country's employability agenda.

Employee satisfaction surveys should be carried out in the institutions to make sure each step in the employee work cycle is treated as a vital force affecting both custom and feat. This is supported by Training Needs Analysis (TNA) which serves as feedback for each key milestone the institutions need to achieve. It will also help the organizations appreciate how they can support their workers to be productive, and where they entail to do more. When done well, employees reach their full potential promptly and make a real contribution to the organization.

Education must bridge the disparity between language flaws and language competence by enhancing the competence of an individual through different programs that highlight the application of English as a method of teaching the lessons. Each course should encourage the use of English in different forms of interaction like reporting, persuading dialogue, and interactive abilities.

The institutions should organize community engagement activities like training and workshops that concern providing instructions in doing household tasks so that threats to attaining an electronically safe environment will be addressed.

The Higher Education Council (HEC) must conduct rigorous evaluation and review of all institutions' programs to guarantee that they foster and support effective communication using the English language appropriately.

The local government must allocate financial support to institutions' programs that aim to improve prevailing skills in English communication that would create an impact on one's performance,

This research should function as the foundation for impending study to build up a more decisive pursuit regarding the value of the English language in achieving an electronically secure location not only in the place where the study is conducted but also in other places with comparable interests.

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